

SOME TYPES OF TRANSFORMATION USED IN SOFAS

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Abstract. This article provides information about transforming sofas, which are an integral part of modern living quarters, and the types of their transformation. Some types of sofa-transformers are considered: "book", "dolphin", "French clamshell", their advantages and disadvantages are noted.

Keywords: transformation, "book", "dolphin", "French clamshell".

Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine a modern house, the interior of a room without comfortable and beautiful sofas. Upholstered furniture is not only a decorative part of the interior, but also home comfort. In general, everyone wants to sit comfortably on the couch and watch TV, read a book or just relax..

Today, there are many models of sofas from various materials, consisting of design features and decorative elements. But the main factor of choosing a sofa is its folding mechanism. "When choosing this component", the main attention should be paid to its convenience, low effort for transformation and the ability to work for a long time.

How furniture meets your requirements depends on its easy and quick layout, which directly affects everyday home comfort. There are many types of folding structures that can be used, but in order to find the right one, the user should pay attention to the following indicators: how often the sofa can be transformed, for example, for a hotel, it can only be transformed if necessary, how much space it takes up when unfolded, you should also pay attention to the presence of a special place for bedding inside the furniture. Some sofas may not have such special seats. If the area of the room is not very large, in this case, selecting the appropriate transformable furniture.

Today all modern sofas are divided into three groups according to the type of transformation. There are:

1. Folding – "book", "tango" or "click-clack", "couch".
2. Retractable (roll-out) – "eurobook", "dolphin", "conrad" or "telescope", "pantograph".
3. Sliding – "French clamshell", "American clamshell" or "sedaflex", "accardion".

In order to understand in detail how the above structures work, let's take a look at the work of some of them.

"Book" – a common and proven method of transformation which transforms into two positions: a sofa – for sitting and a sofa – for sleeping (Pic. 1).

Pic. 1. Sofa - transformer "book": a-for sitting; b-for sleep.

To lay out such furniture, take the sofa seat frame as a basis and raise it slightly until a click is heard in the mechanism and its backrest leans back, as a result of which it becomes a bed (Pic. 2).

Pic. 2. Transformation sequence.

It should be said that during the transformation it is not necessary to move the sofa away from the wall. But there should be a small distance between the wall and the sofa when placing the sofa in the right place.

Sofa “book” has the following advantages:

- very durable;
- the transformation process does not require much effort;
- has a flat sleeping surface;
- suitable for daily use;
- for unfolding the sofa does not require a large place;
- at the bottom of the sofa there is a place for special bedding.

Disadvantages:

- the sofa cannot be placed close to the wall.

Sofa-bed “Dolphin”. The mechanism for unfolding sofas of the "Dolphin" consists of two parts: a rollout or retractable body and a sleeping section located inside. To expand such a sofa, you need to pull the hinges in front. The effort should go forward and slightly up. Thus, the sleeping section emerges from the body and from this came the characteristic name of the mechanism (Pic. 3).

3-rasm. Sofa - transformer “Dolphin”.

Sofa-transformers such as “Dolphin” often have an angular look, because it compactly accommodates the surface of the bed inside, and the shape of the sofa does not change at all. This takes into account the place for placing bedding (Pic. 4).

Pic. 4. Transformation sequence.

The transforming type of sofa – “Dolphin” is quite complicated, and when choosing it, it is necessary to pay attention to the quality of the furniture and the materials of the corpus , because these elements account for the main loads. In addition, these elements need regular cleaning and lubrication. With proper care for such sofas, they will last a long time..

Sofa “Dolphin” has the following advantages:

- easy to use;
- the bed is large and comfortable.

Disadvantages:

- high price;
- regular attention to mechanisms.

Sofa-transformer type “French clamshell”. “French clamshell” refers to sofas that can be transformed to the sleeping surface which formes by the mattress located under the seat, that unfolds in three stages. A modern sofa "French clamshell " can be either regular (straight) or corner. This sofa belongs to the category of very versatile, comfortable and modern furniture (Pic. 5).

Pic. 5. Sofa - transformer “French clamshell”.

“French clamshell” unfolds as follows: the seat cushions remove and under the sofa the mattress with a solid frame, that folds in three layers, takes out. In the unfolded position, the

surface of the bed is quite wide, it is located perpendicular to the back of the sofa, and the mattress leans on strong metal legs (Pic. 6).

Pic. 6. Transformation sequence.

Advantages of “French clamshell”:

– due to its compactness, the mattress takes up less space than other types of sofas because of its triple folding;

– very versatile, it can be used as a guest option or a permanent bed in the bedroom.

Disadvantages:

– lack of storage space for bedding;

– there must be at least 1.5 meters of free space in front of the sofa for transformation.

Summary

The topic discussed in the article is one of the urgent problems in our daily life, because the comfort and coziness of a living conditions is one of the main factors in human life. Therefore, before creating a comfortable environment, a person must have accurate information about furniture suitable for this environment. It is recommended to select furniture that decorates the interior of the room by taking into account some of the transforming features of the sofas..

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